

THE SCIENTIFIC BASIS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF FINANCIAL STRATEGIES OF JOINT-STOCK COMPANIES

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Abstract The financial and economic efficiency of joint-stock companies is largely determined by the financial strategy developed by them. One of the main success factors of most foreign companies is their focus on financial strategy formation and regular monitoring. Effective management of financial and investment activities of joint-stock companies, and learning ways to ensure the growth of its market value in the conditions of the innovation process is one of the urgent issues of the economy, which is of great importance for economic growth on the national and the general market

Keywords: financial resources, joint-stock, company with financial, calculation of economic, external factors.

Today, in our country, by attracting financial resources from the international capital market, we attach special importance to providing joint-stock companies with additional financial resources and increasing the international sovereign credit rating. The transformation of joint-stock companies in participants of the international financial market increases the possibility of introducing innovative technologies into production processes along with increasing their international integration processes. The financial strategy of joint-stock companies is determined by the strategic goals of the company's overall development. We know that the main goal of financial management is to ensure the growth of the owners' welfare, to maximize the company's market value. Therefore, the financial strategy of the company is a general plan of activities for providing the company with financial

resources on time and using them effectively to increase the amount of capitalization. The conditions of the external environment that directly affect the implementation of the financial strategy can be specified in the following four cases:

1. Relative stability of external environmental conditions. Such conditions indicate that the main factors of the external financial environment will gain stability during the strategic period defined by the company.

2. Predicted changes in environmental conditions. Such conditions represent specific fluctuations of the external factors of the external environment noted during the strategic analysis of the dynamics of the upcoming period. Actual fluctuation due to changes in external environmental factors does not significantly differ from the forecast of expected changes in the corresponding stages of the strategic period.

3. Unpredicted changes in the external environment that occur before the period specified in the diagnosis. Such a situation is characterized by new directions of external environmental factors that have a significant impact on the financial development of the enterprise before the period specified in the diagnosis.

4. Unforeseen changes in external environmental conditions. Such a situation is expressed by the appearance of unexpected changes in external environmental factors, that is, the occurrence of undiagnosed changes.

The main diagnostic instruments for determining the description of unexpected changes in the conditions of the external financial environment are the monitoring of the financial market, that is, the overall study of the influence of the dynamics of the loan percentage rate, exchange rate, investment profit standards, the level of insurance tariffs and other separate factors that have an important impact on the financial development of the enterprise.

In our opinion, in international practice, the assessment of the financial potential of joint-stock companies is determined by means of integral indicators - average arithmetic and derivative amounts. When assessing the potential of joint-

stock companies using these methods, it is appropriate to use integrated indicators that include the following stages:

- 1) justification of the selected indicators;
- 2) to assess the stability of joint stock companies according to each indicator;
- 3) calculation of economic, social and environmental sustainability through a multifaceted comparative analysis;
- 4) forming an integral indicator;
- 5) to determine the results with the highest (areas provided with financial and intellectual resources: development potential, diversified and favorable ecological environment) and the lowest stability.

Effective organization of financial support in the management of corporate finance, attracting cheap financial resources, forming the optimal composition of capital by determining the capital price, successfully placing issued securities, having a positive credit history as a result of timely repayment of obligations through the effective use of borrowed funds, shares are open successful implementation of the subscription, determination of the optimal ratio in the reinvestment of the achieved net profit and distribution to dividends. The successful implementation of these tasks serves the success of the corporate structure, the increase in market prestige, and the maximization of business value.

Also, today it is important to develop and implement an effective system of monitoring the implementation of the financial strategy. We formed such a control system within the framework of financial control (special strategic block). In the process of organizing the strategic financial controlling system, it should be taken into account that the level of implementation of the strategic goals of financial development is considered, not the level of implementation of separate strategic measures in the strategic financial development program considered as the object of this type of control. It is precisely in connection with this that targeted strategic financial regulations appear as quantitative standards of this type of control. In

addition, in the process of forming a strategic financial controlling system, we should take it into account that in this case, the control period will be faster and somewhat longer compared to the current financial controlling period. Depending on the type of target strategic financial regulation being monitored, this period can range from one quarter to one year. The rapid financial controlling system controls rapid management decisions on the implementation of financial strategy in the face of unexpected changes in the external financial environment.

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